

RQ#	Primary Papers	
RQ.1	What are the essential characteristics of clinical studies in information system literature?	
	<i>RQ.1.1</i>	<i>What is the contribution type of the study?</i> [R1][R2][R3][R4][R5][R6][R7][R8][R9][R10][R11][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R19][R20][R21][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R31][R32] [R33] [R34]
	<i>RQ.1.2</i>	<i>What is the trend in the number of studies over the years?</i> [R1][R2][R3][R4][R5][R6][R7][R8][R9][R10][R11][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R19][R20][R21][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R31][R32] [R33] [R34]
	<i>RQ.1.3</i>	<i>What are the types of affiliations associated with the authors?</i> [R1][R2][R3][R4][R5][R6][R7][R8][R9][R10][R11][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R19][R20][R21][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R31][R32] [R33] [R34]
RQ.2	What are the requirements and specifications of healthcare/clinical research?	
	<i>RQ.2.1</i>	<i>What does clinical research experience the challenges/requirements?</i> [R1][R2][R3][R4][R5][R6][R7][R8][R9][R10][R11][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R19][R20][R21][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R31][R32] [R33] [R34]
	<i>RQ.2.2</i>	<i>What solutions or use cases does blockchain offer to address these challenges?</i> [R1][R2][R3][R4][R5][R6][R7][R8][R9][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R19][R20][R21][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R31][R32] [R33] [R34]
RQ.3	Have the studies or systems in clinical research been subjected to validation or verification processes?	
	<i>RQ.3.1</i>	<i>What methods are employed to validate study data and the system's performance?</i> [R1][R4][R13][R14][R16][R20][R21] [R22][R24][R25][R28][R29][R32]
	<i>RQ.3.2</i>	<i>Can the study data and methodologies be reused or repeated?</i> [R15][R16][R20][R21][R22][R33]
	<i>RQ.3.3</i>	<i>Have any metrics been determined for the evaluation process?</i> [R1][R4][R13][R14][R17][R20][R23] [R24][R25][R26][R29][R32][R33]
RQ.4	What are the applications of information systems used in clinical studies?	
	<i>RQ.4.1</i>	<i>What is the general category of information system/systems used?</i> [R1][R2][R3][R4][R5][R6][R7][R8][R9][R10][R11][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R19][R20][R21][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R31][R32] [R33] [R34]
	<i>RQ.4.2</i>	<i>What are the requirements or functions associated with using information systems, excluding blockchain?</i> [R21][R24][R31]
RQ.5	What are the applications of information systems used in clinical studies?	
	<i>RQ.5.1</i>	<i>Which primary features of blockchain are intended for utilization with health data?</i> [R2][R3][R4][R5][R6][R7][R8][R10][R12][R13][R14][R15][R17][R18][R19][R20][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R32] [R33] [R34]
	<i>RQ.5.2</i>	<i>Which blockchain platform was used on clinical research/health data?</i> [R1][R3][R4][R5][R9][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R20][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R32] [R33] [R34]
	<i>RQ.5.3</i>	<i>Is the blockchain framework permissioned, consortium or public?</i> [R1][R3][R5][R6][R9][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R19][R20][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R31][R32] [R34]
	<i>RQ.5.4</i>	<i>What types of data are stored on the blockchain, and is off-chain or on-chain data storage utilized?</i> [R1][R2][R3][R4][R5][R6][R8][R9][R12][R13][R14][R15][R16][R17][R18][R19][R20][R22][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R28][R29][R30][R32] [R33] [R34]
RQ.6	What are the requirements for implementing blockchain technology in healthcare research?	
	<i>RQ.6.1</i>	<i>What are the strengths and challenges associated with implementing blockchain technology?</i> [R3][R5][R7][R9][R10][R11][R15][R16][R17][R18][R20][R23][R24][R25][R26][R27][R29][R30][R33][R34]
	<i>RQ.6.2</i>	<i>What solutions are employed to address these difficulties?</i> [R1][R3][R7][R9][R10][R15][R17][R25][R26][R27][R29][R30][R33] [R34]
RQ.7	What services, standards, regulations, and protocols use blockchain technology in the healthcare research domain?	
		[R2][R3][R4][R6][R11][R13][R14][R15][R16][R19][R22][R24][R25][R26][R27][R30][R31][R32][R34]